

Nikiforov-Uvarov versus the $W_0(x)W_1(x)$ Approach to the Hypergeometric Equation

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The hypergeometric DE may be given as (1):

$$p(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + q(x) \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + \text{constant} W(x) = 0 \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{where constant} = -n/2 \left[(n-1) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} p(x) + 2 \frac{d}{dx} q(x) \right] \quad ((2))$$

These two results are used in two approaches, namely the Nikiforov-Uvarov and the $W_0(x)W_1(x)$ methods to solving the Schrodinger, Dirac and Klein Gordon equations. Both may also use the same transformations $y=f(x)$. What differs, it seems, is the constant. In the $W_0(x)W_1(x)$ approach, with $W_0(x)$ being the ground state wavefunction, one decouples $W_0(x)$ from (say the Schrodinger equation) to obtain:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) - 1/m \left(\frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} W_0/W_0 \right) = (E-E_0) W_1(x) \quad ((3))$$

This equation is forced into the hypergeometric form of ((1)) which means that from ((2)) $E-E_0$ will be of the form $n(n-1)a + nb$.

The Nikiforov-Uvarov approach, on the other hand, uses the original Schrodinger equation (or other equations) and incorporates E , the energy eigenvalue, into a quadratic polynomial. A different constant is then set equal to ((2)) with E sitting inside a square root. The result is that E becomes equal to a function that may take on the rough form $[(a n(n-1) + bn)/(c+n)]^2$, which is very different from the W_0W_1 approach.

It seems the two approaches may be used to solve the Schrodinger equation (or other equations) for different potentials. Recently, there have been many articles in the literature using the Nikiforov-Uvarov approach, as it seems to apply to physically relevant potentials.

In this note, we compare the derivations of the two approaches and also consider a potential for which the Nikiforov-Uvarov approach works and the W_0W_1 doesn't. The W_0W_1 approach, however, satisfies a Schrodinger equation for a different potential for which the Nikiforov-Uvarov one does not work.

Derivation of the W_0W_1 approach

One begins with $W_0(x)W_1(x)$, where $W_0(x)$ is a ground state solution (or other level). $W_0(x)W_1(x)$ is inserted into the Schrodinger equation (or other equation) to obtain ((3)) which is then forced to be of hypergeometric form. Often, a transformation $y=f(x)$ is performed first. One may solve for $(d/dx W_0/W_0)$ from ((3)) and use this in the Schrodinger equation because:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{d}{dx} W_0/W_0 \right) + \left(\frac{d}{dx} W_0/W_0 \right)^2 = \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_0(x) \right] / W_0 \quad ((4))$$

Given that one knows the form of $d/dx W_0 / W_0$, one may find a compatible $V(x)$. This approach, however, does not work for all potentials, including some for which the Nikiforov-Uvarov approach works.

Nikiforov-Uvarov (NU) Approach

This approach also uses a product wavefunction $W_a(x)W_b(x)$, although the factors are different. It also focuses on $d/dx W_b(x) / W_b(x)$, but in a different manner. The NU approach applies to a DE of the form:

$$d/dx d/dx W + t_1(x)/s_1(x) d/dx W + s_2(x)/[s_1(x)*s_1(x)] W = 0 \quad ((5))$$

One may see that the energy eigenvalue E is incorporated into $s_2(x)$. Here $s_1(x)$ and $s_2(x)$ are at most quadratic and $t_1(x)$ is linear. The next step is to write $W(x)=y(x) F(x)$, yielding:

$$[d/dx d/dx y] F + y [d/dx d/dx F] + 2 (d/dx y)(d/dx F) + (t_1/s_1)[F d/dx y + y d/dx F] + (s_2/(s_1*s_1)) y F = 0 \quad ((6))$$

The coefficient of y is: $(d/dx d/dx F) / F + (t_1/s_1) (d/dx F / F) + (s_2/(s_1*s_1)) \quad ((7))$ and that of $d/dx y$: $2 (d/dx F / F) + t_1/s_1 \quad ((8))$ after one divides by F .

Next, one multiplies ((6)) by the at most quadratic $s_1(x)$ obtaining an equation of the form:

$$s_1 d/dx d/dx y + t d/dx y + C_1 y = 0$$

If ((6)) is a hypergeometric equation, then the coefficient of y must be a constant C_1 so:

$$C_1 = s_1(d/dx d/dx F) / F + (t_1) (d/dx F / F) + (s_2/(s_1)) = -n d/dx t - n(n-1).5 d/dx d/dx s_1 \text{ from } ((2)) \quad ((8b))$$

Also $2 s_1(d/dx F / F) + t_1 = ax + b$ where $d/dx F / F = d/dx (\ln F)$ (definition)

Then $P = s_1 (d/dx F / F)$ must be linear so its derivative is a constant C_2 .

$$C_2 = d/dx (P) = s_1 (d/dx d/dx F) / F + (d/dx s_1) P/s_1 - 1/s_1 (P*P) \quad ((9))$$

From ((7)) $C_1 = s_1(d/dx d/dx F)/F + t_1 P/(s_1) + s_2/s_1$ thus:

$$0 = C_1 - C_2 + (d/dx s_1) P/s_1 - (1/s_1)P*P - t_1/(s_1) P - s_2/s_1 \quad ((10))$$

This yields a quadratic equation for $P = s_1 \frac{d}{dx} F / F$. In the WoW1 method, it was $\frac{d}{dx} W_0/W_0$ which is the focus of attention. Here F does not equal W_0 .

Solving for P yields:

$$P = \frac{(d/dx s_1 - t_1)/2 \pm \sqrt{[(d/dx s_1 - t_1)/2]^2 + s_2 + k s_1}}{1} \quad ((11))$$

Where $k = \text{constant} = C_1 - C_2 \quad ((12))$

P is a linear polynomial, so the term in the square root must be the square of a linear polynomial.

Given P , one needs $t = t_1 + 2P$ which is the coefficient of $\frac{d}{dx} y$. Then, one has the equation (from ((8b))):

$$-n \frac{d}{dx} t - n(n-1) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} s_1 = C_1$$

C_1 is also given by $C_1 = k + \frac{d}{dx} P$ from ((12)) where k comes from ((11)).

As noted, the Schrodinger energy eigenvalue E_n is contained in s_2 . One must then solve for it leading to an expression with a function of n all squared which is very different from the WoW1 method.

Example

Let us consider an example using the potential:

$$V(x) = V_1 \exp(-2ax) / (1 + q \exp(-2ax)) \quad ((12))$$

This is part of a more general potential used in (2) where the authors solve the Schrodinger equation using the NU method. We try to solve it using the WoW1 approach.

First, the transformation $x = -\exp(-2ax)$ is applied. This converts ((3)) into:

$$\frac{1}{2} 4a^* a z^* z \frac{d}{dz} \frac{d}{dz} W_1 + (2a^* az + 4az g) \frac{d}{dz} W_1 = -m (E - E_0)$$

where $g = \frac{d}{dx} W_0 / W_0$. Thus, $g = (A_1 z + b)/(4az)$ where $A_1 = A - 2A^* A$ if the equation is to be of hypergeometric form. On next applies this to:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_0 - V_1 z / (1 - qz) = E_0 W_0 \quad \text{using:}$$

$\frac{d}{dx} g + g^* g = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_0$. Note: $\frac{d}{dx} = 2az \frac{d}{dz}$. This yields:

$$A_1^2 z^2 + b^2 + 2 A_1 b z - (a/2) z (A_1 z + b) + 2 a^2 z^2 A_1 + (-m) V_1 z^2 4 a^2 / (1 - qz) + m E_0 = 0 \quad (13)$$

Comparing coefficients of z yields:

$$(\text{coefficient of } z^2) \quad (-m V_1)/(4 q^2) - q^2 a^2 A_1 + (a/2) A_1 q - q A_1^2 = 0 \quad \text{yields } A_1(a, q)$$

$$(\text{coefficient of } z) \quad 2 a^2 A_1 + (a/2) q b - 2 A_1 b q + A_1 + A_1 = 0 \quad \text{yields } b(A_1, a, q)$$

$$(\text{coefficient of } z) \quad -q m E_0 - (a/2) b + 2 a^2 b - q b^2 = 0$$

$$\text{constant) } m E_0 + b^2 = 0$$

One may see that the last two equations are inconsistent. Combining the two yields $(-a/2) b + 2 A_1 b = 0$. b cannot be 0 so $A_1 = a/4$ which is inconsistent with the first two equations.

Thus, the WoW1 method does not apply to this potential. It does, however, apply to a potential which satisfies ((13)) with $V_1 z^2 4 a^2 / (1 - qz)$ replaced by $4 a^2 V(z)$ or:

$$-V(z) m 4 a^2 = m E_0 + A_1^2 z^2 + b^2 + 2 A_1 b z - (a/2) z (A_1 z + b) + 2 a^2 z^2 A_1$$

Here a is known and A_1 and b are constants as is E_0 . One may ask whether the NU method may be applied to such a potential. In such a case, one starts with the Schrodinger equation with $z = -\exp(-2ax)$. This yields:

$$4 a^2 z^2 \frac{d}{dz} \frac{d}{dz} W_1 + 4 a^2 z \frac{d}{dz} W_1 - m V(z) - m E_0 = 0$$

where $-V(z) m 4 a^2 = m E_0 + A_1^2 z^2 + b^2 + 2 A_1 b z - (a/2) z (A_1 z + b) + 2 a^2 z^2 A_1$ which is a quadratic $s^2(z)$. This is not of the form of an NU equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to show the different derivations involved in the NU method and the WoW1 approach. It seems each yields very different energy eigenvalue functions of n and applies to different potentials. The NU approach has been applied in the literature to numerous potentials which are of physical importance. It is not clear if potentials compatible with the WoW1 approach are physically relevant.

References

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